

Solvent Extraction Studies of Rare Earths with Hydroxy Dibenzoyl Methane

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The solvent extraction of lanthanum, samarium and dysprosium with hydroxy-dibenzoyl methane (H_2ODBM) has been studied under various conditions. The synergistic solvent extraction of the above mentioned metals and neodymium has also been studied. The extraction constant ($K_{3,o}^*$) and the adduct formation constant ($\beta_{3,o}$) have also been evaluated.

DIKETONES and thiodiketones have been extensively used as extractants. The most widely used ligand is thenoyl trifluoro acetone^{1,2}(HTTA) but recently thiothenoyl trifluoro acetone (HSTTA) have also been shown to be a good extractant³. Not much work has been done with dibenzoyl methane (HDBM) as extractant because of its poor extractability. Recently the studies in the laboratory on the substituted dibenzoyl methane revealed hydroxy dibenzoyl methane as a good extractant⁴. The synergistic solvent extraction of lanthanide β -diketonates in the presence of neutral donors have been a subject matter of great interest. Most of the work has been done with HTTA as acidic ligand⁵.

In this paper the extraction behaviour of lanthanum, samarium and dysprosium with H_2ODBM in benzene solvent is reported. The study on neodymium and europium has already been reported⁴. The synergistic effects of tributyl phosphate (TBP) on the extraction behaviour of Ln/ H_2ODBM in benzene phase have also been reported. The estimation of extracted metal ion was done by indirect methods as already reported^{6,7}.

Materials and Methods

Apparatus: All the extractions were carried out in stoppered separating funnels. The pH adjustments were done by a Photovolt pH meter model 114 with combined electrodes. The optical measurements were recorded with spectromom (201) spectrophotometer of Hungarian make. The shaking was carried out at a constant speed in a mechanical shaker.

Reagents: Stock solution of rare-earths were prepared by the dissolution of their perchlorates, obtained from 99.99% pure oxides in double distilled water. The solutions were estimated gravimetrically by oxalate method.

H_2ODBM and TBP were prepared by methods already reported in literature^{6,7}. Benzene was of

Analar grade and alizarin red S of BDH, LR quality. All other chemicals used were of AR, BDH grade.

General Procedure: 10 ml aliquot of rare earth metal ion solution containing is 135 μ g of metal ion was adjusted to the desired pH and was equilibrated with equal volume of 0.1 M H_2ODBM benzene solution for 3 hours. After equilibration the aqueous layer was drained off and the metal content was estimated in aqueous layer with alizarin red S as reported earlier^{8,4}. Similarly the effect of reagent concentration variation of time at constant pH was also studied.

In case of synergistic extractions studies on the dependence of extraction on hydrogen ion concentration were done by keeping the H_2ODBM concentration (0.04M) and TBP concentration (0.001M) constant and varying pH from 4.0 to 5.5. The solution was shaken for 6 hrs. in each case and kept overnight except Dy when the period of equilibration was 4.5hrs. After separating the layers, the concentration of metal ion was measured in aqueous layer as described earlier^{8,4}. To find the dependence of the extraction on the reagent concentration (H_2ODBM), experiment was carried in which the composition of the aqueous phase was constant but the H_2ODBM concentration in the organic phase was varied in the range 2×10^{-2} to 4×10^{-2} M at fixed pH 5.24 for La; 5.12 for Nd; 5.10 for Sm and 4.94 for Dy) and at a fixed TBP concentration (0.001M). Similarly at a constant reagent concentration (0.04M) the variation of TBP concentration (1.2×10^{-3} to 10^{-2}) was studied. The pH of aqueous phase was kept constant at (5.20 for Nd³⁺, 5.06 for Sm³⁺ and 4.92 for Dy³⁺).

Results and Discussion

The extraction of Ln by H_2ODBM alone can be shown by the following reaction. Subscript (o) denoting organic phase,

with the overall equilibrium constant

$$K_{s,o}^* = D_o [H^+]^{3+} (HODBM)_{(o)}^3 \quad (2)$$

where D_o is the measured distribution coefficient. The extraction of Ln^{3+} into a mixture of H_2ODBM and TBP may be written as :

The overall equilibrium constant being

$$K_{s,n}^* = D [H^+]^3 [HODBM]_{(o)}^3 [TBP]_{(o)}^{-n} \quad (4)$$

Extraction of metal complexes containing OH , ClO_4^- and CH_3COO^- , interaction of TBP with H_2ODBM a solvent molecule or aqueous complex formation by TBP have been assumed to have no significant influence on the extraction equilibria.

From equation (2) and (4) the adduct formation constant can be obtained

$$\beta_{s,n} = \frac{K_{s,n}^*}{K_{s,o}^*} = DD_o^{-1} [TBP]^{-n} \quad (5)$$

which is equilibrium constant for organic phase reaction.

$[H_2ODBM]_{(o)}$ in these expressions is the effective ligand concentration which can be calculated from the relationship

$$[H_2ODBM]_{(o)} = \frac{C_{HA} + P_{HA}}{1 + P_{HA} + K_a/[H^+]} \quad (7)$$

where C_{HA} is the analytical concentration P_{HA} the distribution constant and K_a the acid dissociation constant of H_2ODBM .

Effect of pH : The extraction of lanthanides into organic layer containing only H_2ODBM was very sensitive to pH . Negligible extraction took place at pH values below 3.00 and above 6.5. The maximum extraction for La was at pH 5.9, Sm at 5.5 and Dy at 5.2. The plot of pH vs $\log D$ was a straight line in all the three cases with a slope 3 (Fig. 1). This showed the formation of $Ln (HODBM)_3$.

Effect of Reagent concentration : The extraction increased with increase in reagent concentration (Table 2) the enhancement was large when the reagent concentration was varied from 0.02M to 0.1M but after it there was very little change in extraction with increase in reagent concentration.

Effect of Time : Preliminary experiments were carried out by shaking the layers together for 3 hrs. The time of equilibration was varied under the maximum

Fig. 1. $\log D$ vs pH at constant H ODBM concentration.

TABLE 1

EFFECT OF pH

Total Metal ion strength = 135 μg
Ligand concentration = 0.1 M Shaking time = 3 Hrs.

Lanthanum		Samarium		Dysprosium	
pH	D	pH	D	pH	D
3.75	0.088	3.50	0.0912	3.25	0.0164
4.25	0.033	4.00	0.1742	3.75	0.0321
4.75	0.250	4.50	0.2804	4.25	0.0920
5.25	0.5308	5.00	0.8421	4.75	0.4851
5.75	0.8090	5.50	2.0142	5.25	1.6123
6.25	0.3215	6.00	1.3452	5.75	0.8143

TABLE 2

EFFECT OF LIGAND CONCENTRATION

Metal Ion concentration 135 μg Shaking time = 3 Hrs.

Ligand Concentration	D		
	Lanthanum*	Samarium†	Dysprosium‡
0.04 M	0.2242	0.5321	0.8924
0.08 M	0.6642	1.2248	1.6922
0.10 M	1.3300	2.0142	3.1176
0.12 M	1.8001	2.7634	3.6666
0.16	1.9202	2.8934	4.0021
0.20 M	1.9605	3.0242	4.1294

* $pH=5.9$

† $pH=5.5$

‡ $pH=5.2$

TABLE 3
EFFECT OF pH ON SYNERGISM

Total Metal Ion strength = 135 μ g. Concentration of H ODBM = 0.04 M Concentration of TBP = 0.001 M				Shaking time = 6 Hrs			
Lanthanum pH	D	Neodymium pH	D	Samarium pH	D	Dysprosium* pH	D
4.60	0.0784	4.50	0.0769	4.44	0.0984	4.20	0.1234
4.72	0.5909	4.66	0.1666	4.52	0.2856	4.32	0.4000
4.80	1.4138	4.85	1.0588	4.70	0.9428	4.44	0.8666
5.02	2.8818	5.00	2.5000	4.88	2.0248	4.52	1.5000
5.22	3.9618	5.12	4.3848	5.06	4.1268	4.64	4.1241
5.48	10.6624	5.20	13.0000	5.28	12.3426	4.68	12.2884

* Shaking time = 4 $\frac{1}{2}$ Hrs.

extractable conditions of pH and ligand concentrations. The maximum extractions were obtained in 9 hrs. for La, 5 hrs. for Sm and 4 hrs. for Dy. Once the maximum extraction is reached the increase in period of equilibration has no effect on extraction (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. % Extraction vs time at constant H ODBM concentration and pH.

Stability of complexes : The complexes were stable upto 10 hrs. The organic layer containing the extracted metal ion was shaken with equal volume of water at suitable pH (5.9 for La, 5.5 for Sm and 5.2 for Dy) for periods varying from 1 to 12 hrs. The aqueous layer was checked for the presence of metal ion with alizarin red S. After ten hours of shaking the presence of metal ion was traced in aqueous layer.

As from Table 5 we can conclude that the stability of adducts increases from La to Dy. This is similar to trends obtained in case of HTTA and hydroxy benzoyl acetone (HBA). The adduct formation constant show that H₂ODBM adducts are weaker than the HTTA adducts but are stronger than the HBA adducts. This can be attributed to their order of acidity which decreases in the order HTTA > H₂ODBM > HBA.

Synergism : Distribution ratios are given in Table 3 where the pH is varied at fixed H₂ODBM and TBP

Fig. 3. Log D vs log TBP at constant pH and H ODBM concentration.

TABLE 4

EFFECT OF CONCENTRATION OF H ODBM

Total Metal Ion strength = 135 μ g Shaking time = 6 Hrs.

Concentration of TBP = 0.0001 M

H ₂ ODBM	D			
	Lanthanum	Neodymium	Samarium	Dysprosium
1.98×10^{-3}	1.9245	2.1818	1.7861	1.1462
2.38×10^{-3}	2.6742	2.8888	2.5432	2.0154
2.78×10^{-3}	3.1564	3.6672	3.0421	2.99289
3.21×10^{-3}	4.0425	4.3846	3.9421	3.8652
3.60×10^{-3}	5.1224	5.6625	4.6432	4.7654
3.96×10^{-3}	6.9293	7.1245	5.1242	5.2835

TABLE 5

	$\log K_{3,0}^*$	$\log K_{3,1}^*$	$\log \beta_{3,1}$	$\log K_{3,2}^*$	$\log \beta_{3,2}$
La/H ₂ ODBM/TBP	-13.66	-9.30	4.38	-7.06	6.62
ND/H ₂ ODBM/TBP	-13.04	-8.58	4.46	-6.110	6.94
Sm/H ₂ ODBM/TBP	-12.68	-8.16	4.52	-5.60	7.08
Dy/H ₂ ODBM/TBP	-11.84	-7.10	4.74	-4.68	7.28
Nd/HSTTA/TBP*	-12.82	-6.36	6.46	-3.36	9.86
Eu/H ODBM/	-12.30	—	—	—	—

* Ref-3

† Ref-4

concentration. A log plot indicates slope 3 showing a dependence of three on $[H^+]$ in each case. Fig 3 show the variation of $\log D$ with respect to $\log (TBP)_{(0)}$ by keeping the pH and H₂ODBM concentration fixed. The curve has two segments, one with a slope of about one and another of 2. This suggests that at very low concentrations of TBP (of order 10^{-5}) the adduct formed is Ln (H₂ODBM) (TBP) whereas at higher concentrations (order 10^{-3}) the adducts if Ln(HODBM)₃ (TBP)₂.

The adduct formation constant ($\beta_{3,n}$) are given in Table 5. These values increase with decrease in radii as also shown in case of HTTA. The $\log K_{3,n}^*$ values show an increase from La to Dy. For any particular metal the $\beta_{3,n}$ value for H₂ODBM is lower than HSTTA and HTTA. As we have already stated that H₂ODBM has lower acidity than both HSTTA and HTTA, hence this trend is very much expected. It has already been shown that the adduct formation constant decreases as the acidity decreases*. HSTTA is an exception to this trend because the lower electro negativity of sulfur does not satisfy electron affinity of lanthanides hence increases the tendency to take up TBP molecules.

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